

A Systematic Review on Obesity and Aging: The Two-Stringed Precursors for Osteoarthritis

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Abstract

Osteoarthritis is the most common form of arthritis and a leading global cause of chronic pain and physical disability. Beyond simple “wear and tear” condition, it is now understood as a complex, heterogenous disease involving the progressive breakdown of the entire joint organ. This systematic review adopted a comprehensive search for existing literatures from databases including Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus, and ProQuest, using keywords such as “Two stringed precursor for Osteoarthritis,” “Effect of Obesity on osteoarthritis,” “Obesity and Aging,” and “Effect of Aging on osteoarthritis,” with a time limit from 2016 to 2024, after the review, 33articles were considered eligible to provide sufficient data for the review. Data obtained were summarized to reveal the relationship between obesity, aging and osteoarthritis. Findings revealed that the increasing prevalence of osteoarthritis is highly related to the growing aging population, as well as risk factors, particularly obesity and a sedentary lifestyle in both developed and developing countries. Modification of these factors may reduce the risk of osteoarthritis and

prevent subsequent pain and disability. In conclusion, nurses and healthcare workers should ensure comprehensive health assessments to identify risk factors for early intervention, thereby reducing the impact of osteoarthritis and its associated disability. Additionally, other stakeholders, including the government should intensify health awareness on lifestyle modifications, and efforts should be made at all levels of care to mitigate the negative impact of the disease and reduce its associated complications.

Keywords: Aging, Inflammaging, Obesity, Two-stringed Precursors, Osteoarthritis

INTRODUCTION

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a leading cause of global disability, particularly affecting older adults and women (Chen et al., 2019). It's impact is substantial, ranking as the 20th most common cause of years lived with disability in India by 2019 (Dell'Isola et al., 2020). Hip and knee osteoarthritis are leading causes of global disability, driven by increase in the older population and increased rate of obesity and sport-related injuries (Dell'Isola et al., 2020 & Hall et al., 2021). Knee OA is the most common form, followed by hand osteoarthritis (Peat and Thomas, 2020).

The rising occurrence of osteoarthritis due to the expanding ageing population, along with an increased risk factors such as obesity and sedentary lifestyles, and the consequent disabilities that results, has turned it into a significant public health concern (Chen et al., 2017). According to the Prevalence Trends of Site-Specific Osteoarthritis from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019, prevalent cases of osteoarthritis increased by 113.25% over a 10-year period, from 247.51 million in 1990 to 527.81 million in 2019 (Fan et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2022).

Like the parable of the blind men, who each touched a different side of an elephant and had conflicting descriptions, it is challenging to accurately account for the complete truth when assessing complex and multidimensional illnesses like osteoarthritis (Nedunchezhiyan et al., 2022). In order to make significant progress in addressing this global health issue, it is crucial to prioritize the advancement of comprehensive research in this field. Therefore, this review aims to examine the association between osteoarthritis and two factors that precede it, namely obesity and aging (Nedunchezhiyan et al., 2022).

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This systematic review adopted a comprehensive search for existing literatures from databases including Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus, and ProQuest, using keywords such as “Two stringed precursor for Osteoarthritis,” “Effect of Obesity on osteoarthritis,” “Obesity and Aging,” and “Effect of Aging on osteoarthritis,” with a time limit from 2016 to 2024. Randomized controlled trials and quantitative studies were included.

The initial search yielded about 653 records, records were screened for relevance based on titles and abstracts, after which a total of 620 articles were discarded because of duplicates and non-eligibility and 33articles were considered eligible to provide sufficient data for the review. Non- English studies were excluded due to resource constraints for translation, knowing that this

could constitute potential limitation. Data obtained were summarized to reveal the relationship between obesity, aging and osteoarthritis.

FINDINGS

Obesity and Osteoarthritis

Research has shifted the understanding of the role of obesity in osteoarthritis (OA) beyond mechanical stress to include metabolic factors, previously, it was believed that the leading cause of osteoarthritis was overload on the joints due to excess weight which in turn leads to the destruction of articular cartilage; but findings revealed that obesity increases osteoarthritis risk in both weight-bearing and non-weight-bearing joints, doubling the lifetime risk compared to individuals with normal BMI (Zapata-Linares et al. 2020).

Recent studies have proved otherwise that various other factors like adipose deposition, insulin resistance, and the improper coordination of innate and adaptive immune responses may lead to the initiation and progression of obesity-associated osteoarthritis (Xie et al., 2021; Ramasamey et al., 2021 & Allen et al., 2022). Immune cell interactions, including T cells and B cells, contribute to joint inflammation in obese individuals with osteoarthritis, and understanding these metabolic and inflammatory pathways may reveal new therapeutic targets for osteoarthritis treatment (Zapata-Linares et al., 2020).

There is clear evidence that obesity represents one of the most substantial risk factors for osteoarthritis, especially in the knee, with reports highlighting how obese individuals have three times the risk of developing osteoarthritis (WHO,2018). Obesity is a widely acknowledged worldwide epidemic and according to the World Health Organization (WHO), estimations from 2008 suggest that there are over 1.4 billion persons who are overweight., among them, there are over 200 million men and 300 million women who are classified as obese (Francisco et al., 2018).

Obesity is categorized into three sub-classes such as class I (BMI 30–34.99 kg/m²), Class II (35–39.99 kg/m²), and class III ('morbidly obese' ≥ 40 kg/m²) (Hawker et al., 2023). A relatively recent classification is the category of 'super obese' individuals, defined as individuals with a body mass index (BMI) above 50 kg/m² (Fried et al, 2020). Obesity increases the risk of osteoarthritis in both weight-bearing and non-weight-bearing joints, and doubles the lifetime risk of symptomatic osteoarthritis compared to individuals with a BMI below 25 (Allen et al., 2022).

In addition, a number of literatures indicates that osteoarthritis synovium has enriched number of T cells and B cells compared with healthy ones, hence the interplay between certain immune cells and other cells that reside in the articular joints may constitute a destructive cycle, leading to pathological changes of the articular joints in obese individuals (Allen et al, 2022). Furthermore, current data suggests that the hormone leptin, which is produced by fat cells, plays

a role in this link (Dubern and Clement, 2017; Verzijl et al., 2017). Leptin is present in synovial fluid and its levels are related to BMI. Leptin receptors plays a role in regulating inflammatory and destructive processes in cartilage and other joint tissues, typical obesity is characterized by excessive amount of leptin hormone in the body known as hyperleptinemia and individuals with obesity exhibit an upregulation of leptin gene expression in their adipose tissue (Tsai et al, 2017).

Leptin secretion is controlled by the amount of food consumed, the overall amount of body fat, and several hormones (Nogueiras et al., 2018). Insulin and other pancreatic peptide hormones, including amylin, glucagon, and pancreatic polypeptides have the ability to decrease food consumption and impact the release of leptin (Hamilton et al., 2017). Prolonged increase in insulin levels leads to a rise in the concentration of leptin in the blood plasma (Huang et al., 2024). Leptin is therefore a prominent factor for connecting obesity and osteoarthritis, and it might be targeted by disease-modifying medications for osteoarthritis (Tsai et al, 2017).

Aging and Osteoarthritis

According to Shital et al. (2023), aging is a significant risk factor for the progression of osteoarthritis, a degenerative joint disease characterized by cartilage loss, synovial inflammation, and bone remodeling. More evidence supports that there is a close link between aging and osteoarthritis (Maryam et al, 2017); for instance, age-related changes in chondrocytes, including cellular senescence, mitochondrial dysfunction, and epigenetic alterations, contribute to osteoarthritis development by reducing cartilage homeostasis and regenerative capacity (Lim et al., 2024; Whittaker et al., 2021).

Aging is an intricate phenomenon characterized by the buildup of molecular, cellular, and organ harm, resulting in reduced functioning and increased susceptibility to morbidity and mortality, however, the pace and magnitude of this process differ among individuals (Di Cesare et al., 2021). Bone remodeling plays a crucial role in the structural changes that occur in the joint during the development of osteoarthritis, and the molecular pathways affected by aging significantly contribute to this process (Diekman et al., 2024).

Osteoarthritis among individuals aged 65 years and older is often accompanied by comorbid illnesses, heightened mortality rates, and diminished quality of life (Hsu YI et al., 2021). As people age, especially women after menopause, they lose bone mass due to loss of calcium and other minerals, leading to breakdown of the joints which may consequently result to inflammation, pain, stiffness, and deformity (Diekman et al., 2024). Studies revealed that age-related changes such as genomic instability, telomere attrition, epigenetic alterations, loss of proteostasis, deregulated nutrient sensing, mitochondrial dysfunction, cellular senescence, stem cell exhaustion, altered intercellular communication, and chronic inflammation contribute to the development of osteoarthritis in part by promoting cellular senescence (Hsu YI et al., 2021).

The accumulation of senescent cells in articular cartilage is particularly important, as these cells exhibit a senescence-associated secretory phenotype that promotes inflammation and matrix

degradation (Diekman et al., 2024). It is established that the removal of local senescent cells alleviates the occurrence of traumatic osteoarthritis and promotes the repair of tissue injury (Maryam et al., 2017).

Obesity Control and its Influence on Osteoarthritis

Obesity being a key public health issue promotes the development of osteoarthritis (OA), and patients with obesity often sometimes lack access to nutritional information on how to manage their nutritional intake or implement a healthy diet (French et al., 2022). Land-based exercise therapy is recommended in clinical guidelines for hip or knee osteoarthritis (Liu and Du, 2024). European guidelines for obesity management recommend weight reduction as the non-pharmacological treatment for affected individuals and studies suggested that a 5% body weight reduction produced improved clinical symptoms including pain relief and improvement in functional mobility (French et al., 2022).

Clinical guidelines for knee osteoarthritis encourage diet such as calorie-restricted diet plan and exercise to relieve pain and improve function, including non-surgical treatment strategies such as education, and weight loss. Anti-inflammatory agents such as topical or oral non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, intra-articular injections such as corticosteroids and hyaluronic acid compounds, and additional pain medications such as opioids are recommended for the management of osteoarthritis (Liu and Du, 2024 & Restuccia et al., 2022).

Osteoarthritis Control in the Aged

In the past few years, it has been realized that a complex interaction of multiple factors is involved in the pathophysiology of osteoarthritis, including hypertension being a co-morbidity, especially in high-risked females. Scientific evidence suggests that both land-based and aquatic activities combining aerobics, strength, and endurance programs are safe and effective for patients already diagnosed of osteoarthritis. Controlling hypertension may be beneficial in preventing or reducing knee pain in females with or at risks for osteoarthritis (Restuccia et al., 2022). Also, Vitamin D is a key component for optimal growth and for calcium–phosphate homeostasis, considering the commonly known major musculoskeletal disorders associated with severe vitamin D deficiency, including osteoarthritis, and the possible biphasic effect of vitamin D, Society for Clinical and Economic Aspects of Osteoporosis, Osteoarthritis and Musculoskeletal Diseases (ESCEO) examined the effects of vitamin D on fracture risk, falls or osteoarthritis, and concluded that 1000 IU daily should be recommended in patients at increased risk of vitamin D deficiency (Cai et al., 2021). Understanding these age-related mechanisms has led to the development of potential therapeutic approaches, including Senolytic agents and Senomorphic therapies, which aim to target senescent cells and modify osteoarthritis progression in the aged (Ramasamy et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This review revealed that obesity significantly heightens the risk of developing a wide range of chronic diseases, and its impact on the musculoskeletal system is profound, encompassing both degenerative and inflammatory conditions. Among these, osteoarthritis represents one of the most burdensome consequences. Historically, the connection between osteoarthritis and aging was attributed to the ‘wear and tear’ of articular cartilage caused by continuous mechanical stress. This view has evolved, as contemporary research reveals a more complex and dynamic interplay between obesity and osteoarthritis.

Furthermore, the findings established that osteoarthritis is not merely a consequence of mechanical damage but involves a complex and active response to joint injury, obesity exacerbates the condition by amplifying inflammatory responses and contributing to damage across other joint structures, including ligaments and menisci.

This multifaceted involvement emphasizes the need for comprehensive management strategies that address both the mechanical and inflammatory components of osteoarthritis. Understanding the intricate relationship between obesity, aging and osteoarthritis could guide more effective strategies to mitigate the impact of these debilitating conditions and improve overall joint health and quality of life.

Further research is encouraged to identify the impact of osteoarthritis among obese individuals and the aged, including effective measures to improve awareness among these high-risk groups on the prevention and control of osteoarthritis, in order to mitigate it.

REFERENCES

- Allen, K.D., Thomas, L.M., & Golightly, Y.M. (2022). Epidemiology of osteoarthritis. *Osteoarthr. Cartil.* 30, 184–195. [[Google Scholar](#)]
- Cai, X., Yuan, S., Zeng, Y., Wang, C., Yu, N., & Ding, C. (2021). New trends in pharmacological treatments for osteoarthritis. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 12, 645842. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2021.645842>
- Chen, X., Tang, H., Lin, J., & Zeng, R., (2023). Temporal trends in the disease burden of osteoarthritis from 1990 to 2019 and projections until 2030. *PLOS ONE*. Jul 24;18(7):e0288561–1.doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0288561
- Chen, D., Shen, J., & Zhao, W. ((2017)). Osteoarthritis: toward a comprehensive understanding of pathological mechanism. *Bone Res* 5, 16044 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/boneres.2016.44>
- Dell'Isola, A., Jönsson, T., Ranstam, J., Dahlberg, L.E., & Ekvall, H.E. (2020). Education, Home Exercise, and Supervised Exercise for People with Hip and Knee Osteoarthritis As Part of a Nationwide Implementation Program: Data From the Better Management of Patients With Osteoarthritis Registry. *Arthritis Care Res (Hoboken)*. 72(2):201-207. doi: 10.1002/acr.24033. Epub 2020 Jan 9. PMID: 31325229.
- Di Cesare, P.E., Haudenschild, D.R., Abramson, S.B., & Samuels, J. (2021). Pathogenesis of osteoarthritis. In *Firestein & Kelley's Textbook of Rheumatology*. 11th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier; chap 104.
- Diekman, B.O., & Loeser, R.F. (2024). Aging and the emerging role of cellular senescence in osteoarthritis. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage*. Apr;32(4):365-371. doi: 10.1016/j.joca.2023.11.018. Epub 2023 Dec 2. PMID: 38049031; PMCID: PMC10984800.
- Dubern, B., & Clement, K. (2017). Leptin and leptin receptor-related monogenic obesity. *Biochimie*, 94, 2111-2115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biochi.2012.05.010>
- Fan, Z., Yan, L., Liu, H., Li, X., Fan K., Liu, Q., Li J.J., & Wang, B. The prevalence of hip osteoarthritis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Arthritis Res Ther*. 2023 Mar 29;25(1):51. doi: 10.1186/s13075-023-03033-7. PMID: 36991481; PMCID: PMC10053484.
- Francisco, V., Pérez, T., Pino, J., López, V., Franco, E., Alonso, A., Gonzalez-Gay, M.A., Mera, A., Lago, F., Gómez, R., & Gualillo, O. Biomechanics, obesity, and osteoarthritis. The role of adipokines: When the levee breaks. *J Orthop Res*. 2018 Feb;36(2):594-604. doi: 10.1002/jor.23788. Epub 2018 Nov 28. PMID: 29080354.

- French, H.P., Abbott, J.H., & Galvin, R. (2022). Adjunctive therapies in addition to land-based exercise therapy for osteoarthritis of the hip or knee. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* Oct 17;10(10):CD011915. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD011915.pub2. PMID: 36250418; PMCID: PMC9574868.
- Fried, S. K., Ricci, M. R., Russell, C. D., & Laferrère, B. (2020). Regulation of leptin production in humans. *Journal of Nutrition*, 130, 3127S-3131S. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/130.12.3127S>
- Hall, M., Van der Esch, M, Hinman, R.S., Peat, G., Zwart, A., Quicke, J.G., Runhaar, J., Knoop, J., Van der Leeden, M., Rooij, M., Meulenbelt, I, Vliet Vlieland, T., Lems W.F, Holden MA, Foster, N.E, & Bennell, K.L. (2022). How does hip osteoarthritis differ from knee osteoarthritis? *Osteoarthritis Cartilage.* Jan;30(1):32-41. doi: 10.1016/j.joca.2021.09.010. Epub 2021 Sep 29. PMID: 34600121.
- Hamilton, B.S., Paglia, D., Kwan, A. Y., & Deitel, M. (2017). Increased obese mRNA expression in omental fat cells from massively obese humans. *Nature Medicine*, 1, 953-956. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nm0995-953>
- Hawker, G.A, King, L.K. (2022). The Burden of Osteoarthritis in Older Adults. *Clinics in Geriatric Medicine.* May;38(2):181–92.doi:10.1016/j.cger.2021.11.005.
- Hsu, Y.I., Chen, Y.C., Lee, C.L., Chang, N.J. (2021). Effects of Diet Control and Telemedicine-Based Resistance Exercise Intervention on Patients with Obesity and Knee Osteoarthritis: A Randomized Control Trial. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* Jul 21;18(15):7744. doi: 10.3390/ijerph18157744. PMID: 34360036; PMCID: PMC8345675.
- Huang, J., Zhou, J., Xue, X., Dai, T., Zhu, W., Jiao, S., Wu, H., & Meng, Q. (2024). Identification of aging-related genes in diagnosing osteoarthritis via integrating bioinformatics analysis and machine learning. *Aging (Albany NY).* 2024 Jan 3;16(1):153-168. doi: 10.18632/aging.205357. Epub Jan 3. PMID: 38175691; PMCID: PMC10817387.
- Lim, Y., Wong, J., Hussain, S.M., Estee, M., Zolio, L., & Page, M. (2022). AB0979 Recommendations for weight management in osteoarthritis: a systematic review of clinical practice guidelines. *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases [Internet].* 2022 Jun 1 [cited Aug 18];81(Suppl 1):1616–6. Available from: https://ard.bmj.com/content/81/Suppl_1/1616.1.doi:10.1016/j.ocarto.2022.100298.
- Liu, Y, & Du, G. (2024). Blood pressure is associated with knee pain severity in middle-aged and elderly individuals with or at risks for osteoarthritis: data from the Osteoarthritis Initiative. *BMC Musculoskelet Disord.* Jul 12;25(1):536. doi: 10.1186/s12891-024-07657-x. PMID: 38997710; PMCID: PMC11241900.
- Maryam, R., Giovanna, N., Ali, M., & Masoud, M., (2017). Aging and osteoarthritis: Central role of the extracellular matrix <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arr.2017.07.004> volume 40

- Messier, S.P, Beavers, D.P., Queen, K., Mihalko, S.L., Miller, G.D., Losina, E., Katz, J.N., Loeser, R.F., DeVita, P., Hunter, D.J, Newman, J.J., Quandt, S.A., Lyles, M.F., Jordan, J.M., & Callahan, L.F. (2022). Effect of Diet and Exercise on Knee Pain in Patients With Osteoarthritis and Overweight or Obesity: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA*. Dec 13;328(22):2242-2251. doi: 10.1001/jama.2022.21893. PMID: 36511925; PMCID: PMC9856237.
- Nogueiras, R., Wilson, H., Rohner-Jeanrenaud, F., Tschop, & M.H. (2018). Central Nervous System Regulation of Adipocyte Metabolism. *Regul Pept* (2018) 149:26–31. doi: 10.1016/j.regpep.2007.09.034
- Peat, G., Thomas, M.J. (2021). Osteoarthritis year in review 2020: epidemiology & therapy. *Osteoarthritis and Cartilage*. Feb;29(2):180–9.doi:10.1016/j.joca.2020.10.007
- Ramasamy, T.S., Yee, Y.M., & Khan, I.M. (2021). Chondrocyte Aging: The Molecular Determinants and Therapeutic Opportunities. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*. Jul 14;9.
- Restuccia, R., Ruggieri, D., Magaudda, L., Talotta, R. (2022). The preventive and therapeutic role of physical activity in knee osteoarthritis. *Reumatismo*. May 3;74(1). doi: 10.4081/reumatismo.2022.1466. PMID: 35506320.
- Shital, W., Wu, X., Yogita, S., Sun, A., Fan, X., & Crawford, R. (2023). How are Aging and Osteoarthritis Related? *Aging and Disease* [Internet]. Jan 1;14(3):592–2. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10187698/10.14336/AD.2022.0831>
- Singh, A., Das, S., Chopra, A., Danda, D., Paul, B.J., & March, L. (2022). Burden of osteoarthritis in India and its states, 1990–2019: findings from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *Osteoarthritis and Cartilage*. May;doi:10.1016/j.joca.2022.05.004
- Tsai, M., Asakawa, A., Amitani, H., & Inui, A. (2017). Stimulation of leptin secretion by insulin. *Indian Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 16, S543–548. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2230-8210.105570>
- Verzijl, N., Bank, R. A., TeKoppele, J. M., & DeGroot, J. (2017). AGEing and osteoarthritis: A different perspective. *Current Opinion in Rheumatology*, 15(5), 616-622.
- Whittaker, J.L., Runhaar, J., Bierma-Zeinstra, S., & Roos, E.M. (2021). A lifespan approach to osteoarthritis prevention. *Osteoarthritis and Cartilage*. Dec;29(12):1638–53.doi:10.1016/j.joca.2021.06.015.
- World Health Organization. (2018). Obesity and overweight. Fact Sheet No. 311. Retrieved November 20, 2018, from <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs311/en/>

Xie, J., Wang, Y., Lu, L., Liu, L., Yu, X., & Pei, F. (2021). Cellular senescence in knee osteoarthritis: molecular mechanisms and therapeutic implications. *Ageing Research Reviews*. Sep;70:101413.

Zapata-Linares, N., Eymard, F., Berenbaum F, & Houard X. (2020). Role of adipose tissues in osteoarthritis. *Current Opinion in Rheumatology*. Nov 11;Publish Ahead of Print.doi:10.1097/BOR.0000000000000763